

THE PRODUCTION OF PHOSPHOROUS FERTILIZERS BASED ON KYZYLKUM PHOSPHORITES

¹Jabbarbergenov Madiyar

Intern-teacher of the Department of Chemical Technology, Faculty of
Chemical Technology, Karakalpak State University,

²Khojametova Biybimariyam Kaypovna

Candidate of technical sciences, docent,
Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh.
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7837302>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th April 2023

Accepted: 16th April 2023

Online: 17th April 2023

KEY WORDS

*Fertilizer, phosphorus fertilizer,
phosphorite, Kyzylkum, raw
materials, acid, production.*

ABSTRACT

The production of phosphorus fertilizers all over the world is directly related to the processing of phosphate raw materials and the accumulation of man-made waste. Therefore, the development and implementation of rational and economic technical solutions that ensure the processing of low-grade phosphorites, elimination of waste and reduction of mineral acid consumption is an urgent task. It is for this purpose that the use of Kyzylkum phosphorites for the purpose of fertilizer production is an effective solution. Kyzylkum phosphorites are a low-grade, high-carbon class of phosphorites in terms of composition. However, their ability to react chemically is much higher compared to other phosphate raw materials. Thanks to this, it is important to carry out the production of phosphorus fertilizers from Kyzylkum phosphorites.

Currently, the vision of the path of development passed by our country, the strengthening of competition in the context of globalization requires the development and implementation of the principles and principles of a completely new approach to the development of our state at a more stable and dynamic pace.

Based on the sources presented in these sources, Kyzylkum phosphorites belong to granular types similar to large deposits of phosphorites in Afro-Arab regions. Reserves of phosphate raw materials per 100% P_2O_5 amount to 40.5 tons, which can meet the needs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in phosphorus fertilizers for more than 95 years [2, 121-124].

Separately, it should be said that the main component in the composition of Kyzylkum phosphorites belongs to low-grade ores according to the calculated phosphorus content. The ore contains a large amount of carbonate compounds (calcium modulus – $CaO:P_2O_5=2.85$), clay minerals and organic substances. During the extraction of Kyzylkum phosphorites, phosphorites are divided into several varieties, determining the concentration of the main component of phosphorus in them by the dump-radiometric method. Ultra-low-grade ore is a mineralized mass with a P_2O_5 content of 10-12% and is currently being disposed of as waste.

Since the soils of our republic are neutral and carbonate, direct application of this raw material as a fertilizer without activation is ineffective. The main way to expand the

possibilities of using Kyzylkum phosphate flour is to increase the amount of phosphorus nutrient contained in it absorbed by the plant.

One of the most effective and rational ways of processing low-quality raw materials, the technology of which is being implemented quickly, is the chemical activation of them with a small amount of mineral acids, acid salts and other substances. This makes it possible to organize the production of slow-acting phosphorous fertilizers using unconventional phosphorous, today the conditions of the world market are changing dramatically [5, 65-67].

To obtain a highly concentrated phosphorus fertilizer - ammophos, it is necessary to enrich Kyzylkumphosphorites. Today, at the Navoi mountain-Metallurgical Combine, the particles of the high-grade part of phosphorite containing 19.5-20.5% P₂O₅ and higher are dried and crushed to obtain the exact size, and then classified. Then phosphorite is concentrated to 21-22% P₂O₅ by dry enrichment. The phosphorite flour enriched in a dry way is sent to the furnace compartment, where it is fired at a temperature of 850-900°C. As a result, 85-90% of carbon dioxide is released, and organic matter is completely burned. The phosphorus content in the thermal concentrate formed after the combustion process reaches 24-25%, but the CaO: P₂O₅ ratio remains high (2.05-2.10) [6, 187-189].

Kyzylkum phosphates are phosphates in a form that are not digested by many crops unless they pass into a much more easily soluble form due to exposure to acidic soil. The main purpose of processing phosphate raw materials is the conversion of phosphates into a form that is assimilated by the plant.

When sulfuric acid (57 and higher) of the appropriate concentration is exposed to crushed phosphate raw materials, calcium monophosphate and anhydrous calcium sulfate are formed, hydrogen fluoride evaporates and is captured:

$$[(Ca_3(P_2O_4)_2)]_3CaF + 7H_2SO_4 + 3H_2 = 3Ca(H_2P_2O_4)_2 \cdot H_2O + 7CaSO_4 + 2HF$$
 (calcium monophosphate)

1 ton of acid is consumed per ton of raw materials and about 2 tons of finished products are obtained. Therefore, the phosphorus content in the fertilizer is 2 higher than in the raw material. In the superphosphate filtrate obtained from apatite concentrate, the content of dissolved P₂O₅ is less than 19.5%. On the other hand, growth containing up to 14% of digestible phosphorus (P₂O₅) can be obtained in InKaratagphosphorite. The highest grade of its will be 19.5% obtained during processing into a Karatagphosphoriteproduct, will contain only 14% of the digestible P₂O₅. In addition to the basic reaction between three-calcium phosphate and sulfuric acid, there are other reactions [3, 49-50].

For example, due to an excess of sulfuric acid in insufficiently colored mixing areas, a complete decomposition of trivalent phosphate into phosphoric acid, calcium sulfate and hydrogen fluoride occurs:

Due to this reaction, the higher and first grades of the Kyzylkum product contain significantly more: from 5% to 5.5% phosphoric acid. Phosphoric acid gives superphosphate acidity and hygroscopicity (the standard index does not exceed 12-15%).

In order for the superphosphate to have no acidity, it is neutralized by adding ammonia, lime or phosphorite to it. Naturally, due to incomplete mixing of the reacting mass, two-

substituted calcium phosphate (precipitate) is formed in places of insufficient intake of sulfuric acid, which is also absorbed by the plant. Because it dissolves in weak acids:

$[Ca_3(PO_4)_2]3CaF_2 + 4H_2SO_4 + 12H_2O = 6CaHPO_4 + 2H_2O + 4CaSO_4 + 2HF$ calcium diphosphate

Thus, the composition of phosphate includes the following compounds assimilated by plants: calcium monophosphate, calcium diphosphate and free phosphate acid. Monophosphate and phosphoric acid give from 75% to 90% P_2O_5 . Therefore, diphosphate contains less than 25-100% of the absorbed P_2O_5 . Partially calcium triphosphate remains indecomposable, while a small part of phosphoric acid combines with iron and aluminum (1% iron oxide attaches 2% P_2O_5 , and 1% aluminum oxide attaches 1% P_2O_5). Free phosphoric acid in the superphosphate prevents the formation of gypsum ($CaSO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$), so calcium sulfate remains without water or only one water molecule is attached. It accounts for up to 40% of the fertilizer mass. The color of powdered superphosphate is dark and (obtained from phosphorite), light gray (obtained from Apatite), the smell of phosphoric acid emanates from it.

Under such conditions, the formation of hydroxyapatites and fluorapatites is even possible in the soil. In neutral soils, the chemical absorption of phosphoric acid contained in superphosphate with the formation of two- and three-substituted calcium phosphates reduces the mobility of phosphorus in the fertilizer introduced into the soil.

In conclusion, since the soils of our republic are neutral and carbonate, the use of this raw material as a direct fertilizer without activation is ineffective. The main way to expand the possibilities of using Kyzylkum phosphate flour is to increase the amount of phosphorus nutrient contained in it absorbed by the plant. Kyzylkum phosphorites by composition belong to the category of low-grade high-carbonate phosphorites. However, their ability to enter into a chemical reaction is much higher than that of other types of phosphate raw materials. For this reason, it is important to produce phosphorus fertilizers from red currant phosphorites.

References:

1. Амирова А.М., Соколов С.И., Нарметова Н., Юсупова Ф.М. О вещественном составе зернисто-детритовых фосфоритов Централонных Кызылкумов. // Узб. хим. ж. 1981. №3. С. 8-13.
2. Дехканов З.К., Ибрагимов Г.И., Намазов Ш.С., Садыков Б.Б., Реймов А.М., Сейтназаров А.Р. Химическое обогащение высококарбонатадержащих фосфоритов Кызылкумского месторождения. Горный Вестник. - Навои, 2011. - №2. - С.121-124
3. Кочетков В.Н. Фосфорсодержащие удобрения: Справочник / Под ред. проф. А.А.Соколовского. - М.: Химия, 1982. - 400 с.
4. Гафуров Қ., Шамшидинов И. Минерал ўғитишлаб чиқариш назариясива технология хисоблари. - Т.: Фан ва технология, 2010. - 360 б
5. Технология фосфорных и комплексных удобрений / Под ред. С.Д.Эвенчика и А.А.Бродского. - М.: Химия, 1987. - 464 с
6. Шинкоренко С.Ф., Хрящев С.В., Михайлова Т.Г., Левкина Т.Т. Обогащение фосфоритов Кызылкумского месторождения с применением обжига. // Хим. пром. 1989. №3. С. 187-189.